

NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work natural fibers have been used as reinforcement in thermoplastic based composites and the performances of the obtained composites were examined.

The utilization of straw fibers have shown improved mechanical properties with respect to the neat thermoplastic matrix, consenting also a strong reduction of costs owing to the use of an inexpensive filler. Some chemico-physical modifications of both matrices and reinforcement were performed to obtain a stronger interface between the two phases. Finally the use of PHB, a microbial polyester, as matrix in the preparation of these composites allowed to produce a complete biodegradable material.

Keywords: Natural fibers, thermoplastic, composites, mechanical behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last years natural fibers have emerged as renewable and cheap reinforcement to make structural composite materials (1). Lignocellulosic based natural fibers posses high specific properties, good mechanical behaviour and are abundantly available (2). Among the natural materials straw fibers are in surplus inside the European Community and thus they can be used as an inexpensive filler in the production of natural fiber based composites.

In this work straw fibers were added to two thermoplastic matrices such as polypropylene (iPP) and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), this latter being a polyester produced by bacterial fermentation completely biodegradable.

To obtain a stronger fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion the straw

fibers were previously undergone to a steam explosion treatment that inducing in the lignocellulosic matrices some physico-chemical changes enhances the interactions with the thermoplastic matrix especially when are present reactive functional groups (e.g. carbonyl group in PHB). To render more reactive also the polypropylene matrix it was grafted with a small amount of maleic anhydride: in this way it was possible to increase the interfacial adhesion and consequently improve mechanical behaviour of the composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The PHB samples having a $\bar{M}_w=400,000$ was supplied by ICI- England. iPP and maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (iPPMA) having $\bar{M}_w=178,000$ were provided by Himont-Ferrara-Italy. The wheat straw fibers were supplied by Stazione Sperimentale per la Cellulosa, Carta e Fibre Tessili Vegetali ed Artificiali-Milano-Italy.

Before the utilization, the straw fibers were steam exploded at $T=230^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 minutes.

The composites were obtained by compression moulding.

The percentage of straw fibers used in the composites was up to 50 % weight by weight.

The mechanical properties of the composites were examined at low and high deformation rates (tensile and impact tests).

The interfacial adhesion was evaluated by studying the fractured surface of the samples by scanning electron microscopy analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. PHB/STRAW FIBERS COMPOSITES

The poly-3-hydroxybutyrate (PHB) is a biodegradable microbial polyester. It is a crystalline thermoplastic polymer with a well defined melting point presenting properties similar to that of some conventional polymers (3). Thus PHB has attracted industrial attention as possible candidate for large scale biotechnical products, but its cost and relative low resistance to impact limited till today larger applications (4).

In this work PHB/straw fibers composites were prepared to overcome these disadvantages.

Table.1 reports for all the examined samples, the critical strain release rate, G_c and the critical stress intensity factor, K_{Ic} , calculated according to Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) theory as a function of straw fibers content.

The K_{Ic} and G_c values of composite materials containing 10 or 20 % straw fibers are higher than those of neat PHB, while composite materials containing 30 or 50% straw fibers present about the same values as neat PHB. This indicates that the fiber plays an important role towards the reinforcement of PHB, probably due to the high adhesion between fiber and matrix. In fact, if the adhesion is good a high load is necessary to cause separation of the matrix at the interface, where the stress concentration is maximum.

The result on the fracture behaviour can be interpreted on the basis of fractographics analysis performed by SEM on the

fractured surface of notched specimens. The SEM micrographs were taken near the notch tip in the region of crack initiation. The fracture of neat PHB shows fractures of a very brittle material (see Fig. 1a). No evidence of the formation of cracks and for shear bands is observed. Fig. 1b and 1c show SEM micrographs of the PHB/straw composite materials. These micrographs show:

- a fine distribution of straw fibers in the PHB matrix;
- a very high interaction at the fiber-matrix interface and the presence of some plastic deformation phenomena in the region adjacent to the fibers.

Comparison of the G_c and K_{Ic} values make it evident that 10% and 20% straw seem to be an optimum content for toughening PHB. In fact any further increase in the straw content result in a decrease in the G_c and K_{Ic} values to those of the PHB homopolymer. In conclusion as described the addition of 10%-20 % steam exploded straw to PHB markedly increases the physico-mechanical characteristics of the PHB as a consequence of intermolecular interaction that occur mainly in the amorphous region of the two polymers.

The interactions can be suppose in the formation of hydrogen bonding between the C=O groups of PHB and the hydroxyl groups of the straw, more widely available by the SEP.

In conclusion PHB/straw fiber composites can represent a potential new class of materials that can be find application in sectors such us agriculture mulching, transplantation etc, where biodegradable properties are needed.

3.2 IPP AND IPPMA STRAW FIBERS COMPOSITES

Composites by using as reinforcement steam exploded straw fibers were prepared with two different polypropylenic matrices: a conventional polypropylene ($M_w = 178,000$) and a modified maleic anhydride iPP (MA = 1.6%) (IPPMA). It is known that the presence of maleic anhydride can improve the interfacial adhesion of the polypropylene matrices with lignocellulosic materials (5).

In fig.2 the results of the impact tests performed on both composites series (iPP and IPPMA matrices) are shown. The K_{Ic} (critical stress intensity factor) values for IPPMA based composites seem linearly increase with increasing the straw fibers content, while the K_{Ic} relative to iPP based composites remain almost constant. This good performance of IPPMA composites is probably due to a stronger interfacial adhesion between the two phases and, also to the nucleating action of the maleic anhydride (MA): in fact it produces smaller spherulites and a larger presence of amorphous regions allowing a more pronounced absorption of energy during the fracture tests.

Also in this case the fracture behaviour can be interpreted on the basis of the fractographic analysis performed by SEM on the surface of the notched specimens; the SEM micrographs were taken near the notch tip in the region of crack initiation. Fig. 3a-3b show the fracture surfaces of the neat iPP and IPPMA respectively. The micrographs show a feature of brittle materials. The finer structure found for the IPPMA matrix is attributable to the nucleating action of maleic anhydride.

In the figures 3c-3d are illustrated the fracture surfaces of

iPP80/straw fibers20 and iPPMA80/straw fiber20 composites respectively. The composite having iPPMA as matrix (fig.3d) shows a better fiber-matrix adhesion and higher homogeneity with respect the iPP based composite (fig.3c).

In table 2 the results of tensile tests are summarized. It can point out the following:

- i) The stiffness of the materials (Young's modulus E) increases with the fiber content for the iPPMA based composites, while it remains almost constant in the case of iPP composites samples;
- ii) The strength at break (σ_b) values found for iPPMA based composites are higher with respect to neat iPP matrix, whereas they seem not vary with the straw fibers amount. On the contrary the iPP based composites show a strong decrease with increasing the straw fibers content. These results can be interpreted on the basis of the different produced fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion: in fact the presence of MA is able to bridge the polypropylenic backbone to the OH terminals present in large number onto the exploded straw fibers.
- iii) Finally also the elongation at break point (ϵ_b) values show the similar trend found for σ_b parameter.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion the following conclusion can be drawn:

- The mechanical properties of composites are better than those of neat matrices.
- The performances of iPPMA based composites are superior to those of relative iPP composites.
- PHB/straw composites can represent a new class of biodegradable materials, that taking into account their performances and reduction of costs, hold large perspectives of industrial application.

5. REFERENCES

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Table I Fracture parameters of PHB/straw composites.

PARAMETER	PHB neat	PHB/straw 90/10	PHB/straw 80/20	PHB/straw 70/30	PHB/straw 50/50
K_c	1.8	2.2	2.2	1.8	1.6
G_c	1.1	1.4	1.3	1.1	1.1

Tab.2 Tensile properties of IPP and IPPMA based composites (ASTM D638)

PARAMETER	IPPMA neat (IPP neat)	IPPMA/straw 90/10	IPPMA/straw 80/20 (IPP/straw 80/20)	IPPMA/straw 70/30	IPPMA/straw 50/50 (IPP/straw 50/50)
E (GPa)	1.2 (1.2)	1.3	1.4 (1.3)	1.5	1.6 (1.1)
σ (MPa)	19.7 (15.0)	29.0	27.8 (11.4)	26.2	30.4 (7.8)
ϵ (%)	1.9 (1.4)	2.9	2.7 (1.0)	2.2	2.4 (0.9)

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Fig. 1c

Fig.2 Critical stress intensity factor of iPP and iPPMA based composites as function of fiber content ϕ (ASTM D256)

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 3c

Fig. 3d